

Exponential assessment key for susceptible type leaf BI lesions. Numbers indicate the mean lesion size (mm²) of the respective classes.

Susceptible lesions were further classified into four types (see table). Unpublished data showed that this classification scheme captures the reaction type, the ontogenetic stage, and the presumable sporulation intensity (no. spores/unit of lesion area per unit of time) of lesions. Depending on the research objective, criteria for lesion size and lesion type can be combined or used independently to classify leaf lesions into respective categories by counting.

An example of a record sheet where both lesion criteria are combined and leaf area measurements included is in the table. This scheme provides the basis to determine any of the following parameters

on a per sample or per leaf area basis:
 a) lesion number or lesion area, b) lesion number or lesion area, stratified by lesion type, c) leaf BI severity, d) leaf BI severity, stratified by lesion type, e) relative prevalence of lesion types in terms of lesion number and/or lesion area, f) mean lesion type in terms of lesion number and/

Example of a record sheet for assessing leaf BI, based on a key that combines criteria to characterize lesion size and lesion type.*

Sample number	Lesion size class	Lesion size (mm ²)	Lesion type	Lesions (no.)	Leaf area (cm ²)
	0 (resistant type)	ca. 0.25	A		
	1	2.00	B		
			C		
			D		
	2	4.35	B		
			C		
			D		
	3	9.49	C		
			D		
	4	20.66	C		
			D		
	5	45.00	C		
			D		

*Description of lesion types (based on unpublished data of the relationship among type, age, and sporulation of lesions). A = hypersensitive reaction type lesion that does not sporulate: brown, pinhead-sized spot; B = susceptible reaction type lesion of young physiological age with very high to maximum sporulation intensity: center dark-green, water-soaked to greyish green, no margin or margin purplish green to purplish; C = susceptible reaction type lesion of intermediate physiological age with very high to intermediate sporulation intensity: center greyish green to grey, margin purplish to purplish brown; D = susceptible reaction type lesion of old physiological age with intermediate to very low sporulation intensity: center grey and brittle, margin brown to necrotic brown.

or lesion area, and g) sporulation potential of leaf BI populations. For the last item, the relationship between lesion type and sporulation has to be established experimentally for specific varieties and pathogen races.

This key thus combines most of the features of assessment schemes published earlier while offering higher accuracy, more flexibility, and wider applicability. ■

Determining mating type of *Magnaporthe grisea* population in Bangladesh

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Rice blast (BI), caused by *Magnaporthe grisea* (anamorph *Pyricularia grisea* Cav.), is a destructive rice disease. Modern varieties react differently in recurrent BI epidemics. This suggests the occurrence of different races over time.

New *P. grisea* races can appear through mutation or sexual reproduction, but the latter is unknown in nature. The BI pathogen is heterothallic and mates with isolates from other hosts.

It has been reported that two mating types, Mat 1-1 and Mat 1-2, exist and that they are male, female, or hermaphrodite. Perithecia are produced only when isolates of opposite mating types are crossed. Progeny of such crosses produce the two mating types in equal proportions. Therefore, the potential for sexual reproduction to occur in a population can be obtained from the mating type ratio within the *M. grisea* population.

The mating ability of 73 *M. grisea* isolates obtained from the BRRI BI nursery and from infected fields in the endemic areas of Bangladesh was tested using two Mat 1-1 and two Mat 1-2 standard testers. Three testers were obtained from Dr. J. L. Notteghem of the Institute for Research in Tropical Agriculture, France, and one from Dr. Hei Leung of Washington State University, USA. All the standard testers are fertile, hermaphroditic, and nonpathogenic to rice.

Petri dishes containing oatmeal agar were inoculated with two standard isolates of the same mating type and one of the rice isolates. After 3-5 d of growth, they were placed under fluorescent light at 20 ± 1 °C. After 3-4 wk, plates were

observed for perithecia formation. Among the 73 isolates tested, 46.6% are Mat 1-1 and 20.5% are Mat 1-2. Nearly 33% of the isolates mated with neither Mat 1-1 nor Mat 1-2.

The results show that both mating-

type isolates are prevalent in Bangladesh. Mat 1-1, however, appears to predominate. We are studying the distribution of the mating types by region and identifying isolates that do not mate with either type. ■

Forecasting rice tungro disease (RTD) occurrence in asynchronous rice planting areas on an empirical basis

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The most frequent and serious outbreaks of RTD during the past decade in Indonesia have occurred in Bali Province, where rice is cultivated asynchronously throughout the year. RTD occurrence fluctuates seasonally in Bali and in the country's other asynchronous rice planting areas. The infected area increases around the start of the wet season (WS), reaches its peak in the mid-wet to early dry season (DS), and shrinks toward the late DS. We studied empirical

1. Regression of RTD-infected area in Oct-Dec on that in Jul-Sep in 3 regencies of Bali, Indonesia, 1983-91. Total area planted to rice in Oct-Dec averaged 24,400 ha.

rules of RTD occurrence in WS in Badung, Tabanan, and Gianyar, the major RTD-endemic regencies of Bali.

Analyses were made with data from Apr 1983 to Mar 1991. Data on monthly rainfall and RTD-infected area were obtained from pest observers' reports. The Bali Provincial Agriculture Service provided relevant agriculture statistics. In Badung, Tabanan, and Gianyar, rice was cultivated in WS on an average of 19,300, 29,800, and 16,000 ha, respectively, and in DS on 16,700, 21,900, and 16,600 ha during the 8-year period.

The RTD-infected area in Oct-Dec (transition to early WS) is positively related with that in Jul-Sep (second half of the DS) when RTD incidence is lowest in a year (Fig. 1). Rainfall, mean temperature, and the area planted with

vector-susceptible cultivars failed to account for significant additional variance in the infected area in Oct-Dec.

The RTD onset month (defined as the month when the newly infected area was greater than twice that of the previous month and increased more than 1 ha) tended to precede the start of WS (monthly rainfall > 200 mm) in years of severe occurrence where infected area in WS was 100 ha. In ordinary years, RTD onset month often came after the beginning of WS (Fig. 2). The difference in RTD onset month relative to that of the WS between the two categories of years is significant (Mann-Whitney U-test, $p < 0.05$).

RTD occurrence in Bali in the 1990-91 WS was successfully forecast using these empirical rules. ■

A procedure for miniscale preparation of *Pyricularia grisea* DNA

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DNA from the blast (BI) pathogen *Pyricularia grisea* can be prepared inexpensively in 1.5-ml microcentrifuge tubes in sufficient quantities for several

Southern hybridizations and polymerase chain reaction experiments. We found that the potassium acetate extraction method can be successfully applied to ground mycelia. The isolated DNA is sufficiently pure to allow digestion with restriction enzymes, making organic solvent extraction optional. Using the following method, DNA can be conveniently extracted from 100 samples

2. Relationship in the starting months between RTD onset (solid circles) and WS (open circles) in 3 regencies of Bali. Stars denote WS of severe RTD occurrence.